

IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF ADVERTISING ACTIVITY IN ENTERPRISES

Author: Abduvohidov Behzod xxx,

Teacher of the Department of Digital Economics at the Denov Institute of

Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy tel: +998996229700

e-mail: bekabduvohidov97@gmail.com

Annotation

Increasing the effectiveness of advertising activities of enterprises, especially textile enterprises, and organizing the efficient use of funds directed by enterprises to the advertising process is one of the most urgent topics today. In order to increase the practical importance of this scientific article, the advertising activity and marketing status of the member enterprises of the association "O'zto'qimachilik sanoat", which unites local textile enterprises, was analyzed based on statistical data and analytical methods. we studied.

Аннотация

Повышение эффективности рекламной деятельности предприятий, особенно предприятий текстильной промышленности, и организация эффективного использования средств, направляемых предприятиями на рекламный процесс, является одной из наиболее актуальных тем на сегодняшний день. В целях повышения практической значимости данной научной статьи на основе статистических данных и аналитических методов проведен анализ рекламной деятельности и маркетингового статуса предприятий-членов ассоциации «O'zto'qimachilik sanoat», объединяющей местные текстильные предприятия.

Keywords: advertising, digital marketing, digital advertising, marketing strategies, e-commerce.

Ключевые слова: реклама, цифровой маркетинг, цифровая реклама, маркетинговые стратегии, электронная коммерция.

The world's experience in today's global process shows that the country and its enterprises and organizations are provided through the existence of a national electronic and digital system with advanced socio-economic development and its competitiveness in the foreign market. According to GCDBT (Global Center for Digital Business Transformation), if digital transformation does not take place soon, businesses that focus on the digital revolution, or digital marketing, will squeeze 40 percent of the leading companies out of the market in the next 5 years. Therefore, after that, it would be considered necessary for any company to take into account the strategies of the incentive market in the development of its development strategy.

The power and importance of advertising is known from world experience. It incorporates information that first has emotional colors given in a compact, artistically expressed form and conveys the most important facts and information about goods and services to the minds and attention of potential buyers. At the same time, it should be noted that advertising is always information, but information is not always advertising. Sales advertising should promote customer service quality. With advertising, customers quickly find the goods they need, buying them conveniently and with little time. In this case, the sale of goods will accelerate, the productivity of sales personnel will increase, expenses will decrease.

Special areas of advertising activity	Advertising work
Economy	Production, trade, finance, workforce offer, job search

Household appliances	Sewing and preparing household goods and recreation items.
Rwith intellectual (mental) service	Education, medicine, books, press, prophecy, tourism
Views	Circus, theatre, concerts
Religion	Missionary summons, religious posters, invitations to religious ceremonies
Politics	Election candidates, rallies, demonstrations, manifestoscies (mass marches) slogans
Jurisprudence	Reports of lost people, search for criminals, inviting them to lawsuits
Charity	News of charity services, calls for donations
Science and ecology	Promotion of educational areas in advertising, sheets, posters, prospects, tracts
Family and interpersonal relations	Marriage announcements, invitation to get acquainted, travel together, start work

1- Image . Classification of types of advertising activities¹

The peculiarities of advertising are: lack of integrity; appeal within a paid place or time; to make the identity of the beneficiary clear; multiflectionality; final uncertainty of the result.

Important features of advertising engagement include:

1. advertising is the process of public communication;
2. use ril manipulation tools;
3. advertising affects the human psych;

¹ Karrieva Yo.K., Nematov I.U., Masharipov A.A., Egamaliyev Yo.I., Abdurahimov S.N., Baxronov A.SH. Organization of advertising activities: Learning Manual .-T.:TDIU, 2009.-132 b.

4. diversity of advertising forms;
5. the social and cultural nature of communication.

Advertising promotes good product sales and speeds up the mallement of a bad product. It shows what qualities the product does not have and helps the consumer to quickly understand it. An advertisement that the consumer himself cannot identify, that names the distinguishing features of the product, helps to determine whether the feature is nearly none, thereby speeding up the failure of the product.

Advertising – the type of products produced by production or product consisting of distributing information paid by production, service enterprises and public organizations, or other types of products made by product, and affecting the mass or individual mind, provokes a certain reaction from the select audience.

Advertising has a huge impact on the worldview of society. The impact of advertising on society is divided into social and economic functions. First, the social cultural impact that advertisements have on the worldview of society is divided into useful and harmful effects. Advertisements act as a way of educating consumers to do business and fostering a popular consumer culture by raising the level of their lifestyle. For example, companies that protect the interests of society (such as preventing the control of a car by consuming alcohol) provide consumers with socially necessary consumption and useful information for them. The culturally good function of advertising is that it shows the generation of time that the ad was created and their culture, sometimes it becomes the fashion of that time. On the contrary, advertising can sometimes also promote elements of an undesirable culture that are not true of society. Such advertising is a bad side that prevents the consumer from choosing the right product. Second, advertising performs both economically and positively negative functions. Advertising, generating effective demand, allows for mass production, performs positive functions such as helping to save society money by lowering the cost of a product, as well as creating competition between companies in protecting consumer rights and interests. On the contrary, there are also criticisms that advertising allows the

right choice of consumers, increases product identification and market prices, strengthens the market share of large companies and increases the monopoly power of companies.²

There are four universal functions that any advertisement performs:

1. Economic function.
2. Social function.
3. Marketing function.
4. Contact function.

In recent years, digital **marketing** has developed very quickly around the world and in our country, which of course is linked to the popularity of the Internet. According to some reports, Internet users now make up 57% of the world's population. People spend an average of 6 hours and 42 minutes every day online, by the end of 2022, more than 73% of all eCommerce sales are estimated to fall off mobile devices. This means that there is a huge amount of time and opportunity to pursue digital marketing activity.

Digital marketing is a component of marketing that uses online digital technologies such as Internet and desktop computers, mobile phones and other digital platforms to advance products and services. Its development in the 1990s and 2000s changed the way brands and businesses use technology for marketing. Once digital platforms are increasingly included in marketing plans and everyday life, people are increasingly using digital devices instead of going to physical stores, and digital marketing activities are rampant.

Digital marketing has a number of important advantages over traditional marketing:

It allows you to engage with a wider audience and find customers even in unexpected locations. This provides the ability to transcribe product and company data to a large number of consumers in a short time period, while other

² Karrieva Yo.K., Nematov I.U., Masharipov A.A., Egamaliyev Yo.I., Abdurahimov S.N., Bachronov A.SH. Organize advertising activities: Learning Manual .-T.:TDIU, 2009.-132 b

strategies require significant time costs.

1. It allows you to establish communication with customers.
2. Digital technology helps customers to be more affected, increasing the likelihood of interest in the product.
3. Digital advertising is cheaper than other strategies.
4. Transparent observation of the effectiveness of the effect.

U.S. Programmatic Ad Spending and % of Total Display Ad Spending

iab. IAB Proprietary Research
 Source: <https://www.emaze.com/news/media/mediapost.com/uploads/ProgrammaticMarketingForecast2019.pdf>

2 - image. Software advertising market share in US digital advertising market³

³ <https://www.tadviser.ru/index.php/>

3 - image. The most effective digital marketing methods according to vendors worldwide in 2020⁴.

From a strategic marketing point of view, the customer needs to solve the problem solved using that product, not the brand itself. The solution is achieved using a variety of technologies, and the technologies themselves are changing relentlessly. The role of strategic marketing is to identify different existing or pending markets or segments of the connection based on tracking the evolution of the given market and analyzing the needs that need to be satisfied. The first step in implementing a marketing strategy, i.e. case analysis, will allow you to identify market opportunities, identify market segment, determine your own strengths and weaknesses of the company. Market analysis results serve as the basis for developing a marketing strategy.

Taking into account the consequences, the **Manufacturing** Society also tried

⁴ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/190858/most-effective-online-marketing-channels-according-to-us-companies/>

to analyze the marketing situation and, as a result, to find a positive solution. We know that one of the most important tasks of marketing activity is the sale of manufactured products and goods or existing types of services, so the main focus of the Manufacturing Society is on exporting textiles and goods to foreign markets, so it is appropriate to study the export safety indicators that the association has been returning to in recent years. Table 1 of the following states: "According to the Export Nomenclature of the Manufacturing Society for 2019-2021, a total of **\$2,931 billion (U.S.) in textiles were exported in 2021, of which \$1,618 billion (U.S.) was exported to yarn products, The equivalent of \$145 million (U.S.) in gas fabric, \$238m (U.S.) in tricotage products, \$882 million (U.S.) in sewing products, and \$46.3 million (U.S.)**. We will also see that the 2021 annual total growth figure was 155%. Of course, it is only natural for the Manufacturing Union to look very good at the picture of export potential growth from the above indicators, but the main reason for these high-level indicators can be said to be the impact of 2020's quarantine around the world because we know that this year, like many industries, the international trade process in textile sectors has stalled.

Table 1

“O’zto’qimachilik sanoat” Union Export Nomenclature for 2019-2021⁵
(mln \$)

№	Product Name	2019 year		2020 year			2021 year		
		value	share	value	share	growth	value	share	growth
	Jami	1596,4	100,0	1885,7	100,0	118,1	2931,2	100,0	155%
	Rope squid	928,8	58,2	906,0	48,0	97,5	1618,7	55,2	179%

⁵ “O’zto’qimachilik sanoat” uyushmasi malumotlari asosida muallif ishlanmasi

Gas Fabric	78, 0	4,9 %	103,9	5,5 %	133, 1%	145,6	5,0 %	140%
Knitting fabric	79, 3	5,0 %	139,7	7,4 %	176, 3%	238,3	8,1 %	171%
Sewing knitting products	489, 1	30,6 %	706,3	37,5 %	144, 4%	882,3	30,1 %	125%
Sock products	21, 2	1,3 %	29, 8	1,6 %	140, 9%	46, 3	1,6 %	155%

In conclusion, modern marketing is undergoing new changes every day, which is why consumer goods change day by day and modern digital technology becomes part of people's lives, so enterprises in our country are especially full textile-adapted enterprises are required to use digital marketing strategies to strengthen their place in the future market, and the focus is not just on products and services, but companies see themselves as experts in their fields in the digital world and will have to offer customized content for target groups

Why do we offer to use digital marketing in the advertising process of our wedgies?. In our opinion, digital marketing has three main advantages over traditional marketing method – **measureability, affordability, speed.**

That it can be measured. A website is definitely the most important marketing tool to understand what people are interested in and how they find your website and how it moves around it. How many people have visited the enterprise site, where they come from, natural search, click payment (PPC), via social media or email campaigns, you can track changes in your numbers over time, giving us a real idea of whether our marketing message is reaching people right.

Affordability: Digital marketing has opened up the marketing space for small and medium-sized firms around the world and put

them on an equal playing field with large corporations because of their affordability. For example, Facebook ad campaign tools such as "boost posts" make up a fraction of the cost of printing and can be redirected to a specific group of people.

At the same time, less paper goes to the police station to get more extensive communication and upload with a wider audience that covers the globe. Similarly, online banner ads on websites generally stand for less than ads posted at traditional outlets, such as daily newspapers or magazines. With information generated using this online promotional technique, the business will also get feedback on how effectively you spent advertising.

Speed. in a virtual world, you can get your messages faster – all you need to do is click the mouse button. Compared to the relatively long-lasting process of producing and distributing printed materials, this means that companies are much quicker to send their messages.

One of the biggest reasons why digital marketing has become so important is engagement – we can talk to our prospective and current customers, answer questions, and solve problems. Participation can also be done through other ways, such as contests, blogs, PR, events and other marketing events.

Why does the fashion industry need a digital marketing strategy? because without it, we miss opportunities and lose our business. Formulating a digital marketing strategy helps us to make conscious decisions about accessing the digital marketing arena and ensures that our efforts are focused on the digital marketing elements most relevant to the enterprise.

We can make the following proposals to improve the efficiency of advertising activities of companies that are part of the fire and to promote the Sovdo process:

1. Recruitment of marketers with a high level of knowledge of modern marketing in corporations.
2. Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these answers with you.

3. Each company should choose consumers with information about the company by introducing its own seo system because the consumer begins to look for the product he needs on the Internet in the first place

4. Each company must open its own social networks page, ensuring mutual communication with consumers and eliminating shortcomings and shortcomings;

5. O'zbekiston to'qimachilik sanoat uyushmasiga a'zo korxonalar birlashgan xolda o'zlarining maxsulotlari uchun elektron savdo platformasini yaratishi lozim.

The conclusion is that digital marketing offers new possibilities for the advertising and promotion process, not only in the textile industry, but also in other industries.

LIST OF AVAILABLE LITERATURE

1) Karrieva Yo.K., Nematov I.U., Masharipov A.A., Egamberdiev Yo.I., Abdurahimov S.N, Baxronov A.SH. Reklama faoliyatini tashkil etish: O'quv qo'llanma .-T.:TDIU, 2009.-132 b.

2) Abduxalilova L.T. Internet marketing . O'quv qo'llanma . -T .: TDIU , 2011. - 211 bet .

3) Ahmedov 1. , Jalolov J. , Akromov T. , Nematov 1. Marketing tadqiqotlari . O'quv qo'llanma - T . : Iqtisodiyot , 2011-95 b .

4) www.stat.uz - O'zbekiston Respublikasi Davlat statistika qo'mitasi

5) <https://www.statista.com>